

ABSTRACT

Drug targeting to specific sites creates a challenging task for the formulation designer. These problems may be solved by the formulating the vesicular carrier system with in micro size range. Microsponges is microtechnology based formulation which offers controlled release of drug at the target site. Budesonide is a glucocorticoid steroid used for the treatment of several colonic diseases like chron's disease, ulcerative disease and colon cancer. The low water solubility and poor bioavailability of budesonide is the challenging problem facing by the formulation scientist. It can be overcome the above problem by increase the solubility to increase the dissolution rate as well as bioavailability. The small size and porous nature of the novel delivery system they can easily bind to poorly-soluble drugs within their matrix and prevent drug from rapid metabolism and excretion, improve their bioavailability. The microsponges of budesonide is prepared by quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method. Further the formulated microsponges are evaluated for its phase particle size determination, Loading Efficiency, Production Yield, SEM, FTIR, DSC, XRD and in-vitro release study.

Keywords-Microsponges, Budesonide targeting drug delivery and colloidal carrier.

INTRODUCTION

Dosage forms- Dosage forms are the means by which drug molecules are delivered to sites of action within the hold body. Dosage forms are mainly contains active drug components also known as active pharmaceutical ingredients and non-drug components that is known as excipients. Dosage forms contains various types such as solid, liquid, gaseous and semisolid dosage forms.

Types of dosage forms- Dosage forms are mainly divided according to the route of administration and physical form of material.

(a) Based on route of administration

Oral , Inhaled , Topical , Ophthalmic, Parentral , Vaginal and Rectal.

(b) Based on physical form

Solide.g: Tablet, capsule

Semi solid e.g: Suspension, emulsion

Gases e.g: Aerosols

Sustained release drug delivery system - A sustained release drug delivery system provides a therapeutic blood level of the drug which is attained rapidly and is maintained within therapeutic limits over extended period of time usually 10 to 12 hours. After attaining the desired therapeutic range attempts are made to make the drug available at a rate proportional to the elimination rate of the drug from the body. Such drugs also referred to as prolonged action drugs because the effect of the drug is extended over a prolonged duration of time. Repeat action dosage forms are also aimed at providing prolonged action.

Controlled drug delivery system- Controlled release dosage forms provide better control of plasma drug levels, less dosage frequency, less side effect, increase efficacy and constant delivery. Control release means any drugs delivery system maintains adequate and desired release of drug over extended period of time. Hydrophilic polymer matrix is widely used for a formulating controlled dosage form. The oral controlled drug delivery was some potential advantage like controlled release rate and dose maintenance in the plasma.

Advantage-

Reduced dosing frequency and dose reduction and improved patient compliance.

Reduced toxicity due to overdose constant level of drug concentration in the blood plasma. The night time dosing can be avoided.

Fig 1.1- Plasma drug concentration profile curve

Targeted drug delivery system- Targeted drug delivery is kind of smart drug delivery system which is miraculous in delivering the drug to a patient. Targeted drug delivery system is based on the method that delivers a certain amount of a therapeutic agent for a prolonged period of time to targeted diseased area with-in the hole body. This is helps maintain the required plasma and tissue drug levels in the hole body, therefore avoiding any damage to the healthy tissue via the drug. Ideally targeted drug delivery system should be biochemically inert, should be non-immunogenic, should be physically and chemically stable in-vivo and in-vitro conditions and should have restricted drug distribution to target cells or tissues or organs and should have uniform capillary distribution. A targeted drug delivery system is preferred over conventional drug delivery system due to three main reasons.

TYPES OF TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY-

1-Active targeting 2- Passive targeting

1- Active targeting- Active targeting means a specific ligandreceptor type interaction for intracellular localization which occurs only after blood circulation and extravasations. This active targeting approach can be further classified into three different level of targeting which are:-

First order targeting refers to restricted distribution of the drug carrier system to the capillary bed of a predetermined target site, organ or tissue. eg:- Plural cavity, eyes and joints.

Second order targeting refers to selective delivery of drugs to specific cell types such as tumour celled and not the normal cells. eg:- Kupffer cells in liver.

Third order targeting refers to drug delivery specifically to the intracellular site of targeted cells.

2- Passive targeting:- It refers to the accumulation of drug or drug carrier system at the specific site such as anti-cancerous drug whose explanation may be attributed to physicochemical or pharmacological factors of the disease. In the case of cancer treatment the size and surface properties of drug delivery nano-particles must be controlled specifically to avoid uptake by the reticulo-endothelial system to maximize circulation time and targeting ability.

COLON SPECIFIC DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM- Colon drug delivery system refers to targeted delivery of drug in to the lower part of gastrointestinal tract, mainly large intestine. Colon targeting drug delivery system may be follow by the concept of sustained or controlled release drug delivery system for the colon targeting drug delivery system for oral routes of administration has received most attention. The colon targeted drug delivery system is beneficial for the treatment of several colonic diseases mainly inflammatory bowel diseases, colonic cancer, infection diseases.

ANATOMY OF COLON- Colon is a 1.5m long. Colon started from the distal end of the ileum and exit at the anus section. The colon is situated the upper 5 feet of the large intestine portion and it situated in the abdomen part and colon is a cylindrical tube structure. The colon are dividing in four parts-

Ascending colon:- Ascending colon begins at the cecum, where it joins the end of the small intestine and travels upward along to the right side of the human body the transverse colon.

Transverse colon:- Transverse colon connects to the ascending colon to the descending colon and lies across the upper abdomen.

Descending colon:- Descending colon connects the transverse colon and sigmoid colon and lies along the left side of the human body.

Sigmoid colon:- Sigmoid colon connects to the descending colon and the rectum.

Fig-1.2 Structure of large intestine

Table - pH and residence time of different parts of colon-

Segment	Residence time in min.	pH
Ascending colon	360 ^a	6.5
Transverse colon	240 ^a	6.5
Descending colon	360+240 ^a	6.8

Advantage of colon drug delivery system:- The colon targeting drug delivery system are used in treatment of inflammatory bowel diseases like ulcerative colitis, crohn's disease etc. Colon targeting system is Decreases the side effect in the treatment of colon diseases.

Disadvantage of colon drug delivery system:- The main disadvantage of colon delivery of drug is poor site specificity. The pH level in the small intestine and caecum are similar which reduce site specificity of formulation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Table - Chemicals and its manufacturers-

INGREDIENTS	PURPOSE	SOURCE
Budesonide	Pharmaceutical active ingredient	Yarrow Chem. Products mumbai
Eudragit L-100	Polymer	S D fine Chemicals
Ethyl cellulose	Polymer	Loba. Chemicals. Mumbai
DCM	Plastisiser	S D fine Chemicals
PVA	Coating material	Loba. Chemicals. Mumbai
Ethanol	Solvent	Changshuyangyuan chemical
Methanol	Solvent	Changshuyangyuan chemical
Distilled Water	Solvent	Laboratery prepare
Potassium-dihydrogen phosphate	Buffer	Finar limited

METHODS-

PREFORMULATION STUDY-

(A) DETERMINATION OF (λ_{max}) IN PHOSPHATE BUFFER (pH6.8)-

Preparation of phosphate buffer (pH-6.8)- Phosphate buffer of (pH6.8) was prepared as per I.P.-

Solution 1- Take 28.80 gm of disodium hydrogen phosphate was dissolved in distilled water in 1000ml volumetric flask which was sonicated in the bath sonicator so that it get the dissolved easily, further the volume was made upto the make with distilled water.

Solution 2- Take 11.45gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was dissolved in distilled water in 1000ml volumetric flask which was sonicated in the bath sonicator so that get dissolved easily, further diluted water in added to make up to volume. The solution 1 (500ml) and solution 2 (500ml) was mixed and prepared the phosphate buffer(6.8).

Preparation of stock solution-

The stock solution of budesonide in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) was prepared by 100mg drug was weighted and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted with phosphate buffer and make to get the concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of solution. From 1ml solution was pipette out into 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was make up to with phosphate buffer (pH6.8). The solution was scanned in UV range between 200-400 nm UV spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the working solution-

The prepared stock solution was subsequently diluted with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 in 10 ml volumetric flask to get 20,40,60,80,100,120,140 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The resulting solution absorbance was measured at wavelength of 246nm using UV spectro-photometric against blank of pH 6.8 buffer.

(B) DETERMINATION OF (λ_{max}) IN METHANOL- The absorption maximum (λ_{max}) for budesonide in methanol was determined by scanning the drug solution within the range of 200-540nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer and obtain value was compared with standard and absorbance maximum value was reported.

Preparation of stock solution- The stock solution of budesonide in methanol was prepared by dissolving 100mg of drug in 100ml methanol in 100ml volumetric flask to get 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of solution. 1ml of sample was withdrawn into 100ml volumetric flask and volume make up with methanol . The solution was then scanned inUV-spectrophotometer.

Preparation of working solution- The prepared stock solution was subsequently diluted with methanol in 10 ml volumetric flask to get 50,100,150,200,250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.The resulting solution absorbance was measured at wavelength of nm using UV

spectrophotometer against blank of methanol. The calibration curve are plotted of absorbance versus concentration. The results are shown in table .

(C) DETERMINATION OF λ_{max} IN 0.1N Hcl-

Preparation of 0.1N Hcl- Take 8.4ml of Hcl and diluted with distilled water in 1000ml volumetric flask and measured the pH by digital pH meter.

Preparation of stock solution- The stock solution of budesonide in 0.1 N Hcl is prepared by dissolving 100mg of drug in 100ml 0.1 N Hcl in 100 ml volumetric flask to get 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution. 1ml of sample was withdrawn in 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted with 100ml 0.1 N Hcl. The solution was scanned in UV range between 200-400 nm UV spectrophotometer.

Preparation of working solution- The prepared stock solution was subsequently diluted with 0.1N Hcl in 10ml volumetric flask to get 20,40,60,80,100,120,140 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The resulting solution absorbance was measured at wavelength of 246 nm using UV spectrophotometer against blank of 0.1N Hcl.

(D) DETERMINATION OF λ_{max} IN WATER- The absorbance maximum (λ_{max}) for budesonide in water was determine by scanning the drug solution within the range of 200-400 nm using UV spectrophotometer.

Preparation of stock solution- The stock solution of budesonide in water is prepared by dissolve 100 mg drug in 100 ml water in 100ml volumetric flask to get 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution. 1ml of sample was withdrawn in 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted with 100 ml water. The solution was scanned in UV range between 200-400 nm UV spectrophotometer.

Preparation of working solution- The prepared solution was subsequently diluted with water in 10 ml volumetric flask to get 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The resulting solution absorbance was measured at wavelength of 246 nm using UV spectrophotometer.

DETERMINATION OF PARTITION COEFFICIENT- Partition coefficient was determined by shake flask method. Take distilled water and n-octanol in separating funnel and continuous shaking for 30 min. weighed amount of budesonide was added to separating funnel and again shaking for 2hr to achieve drug distribution in both phases. The separating funnel were allowed to stand for 24hrs. Both aqueous and organic layers were separated and analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at 200-400 nm. The absorbance value was recorded. Drug having value of $\log P > 1$ are classified as the lipophilic and $\log P < 1$ are indicated of hydrophilic drug.

$$P_{o/w} = (C_{oil}/C_{aq.})_{equilibrium}$$

DRUG-EXCIPIENT INTERACTION STUDIES-

1. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy- FTIR spectra was obtained by FTIR spectrophotometer. The physical mixture drug and excipient was contained in glass vials, seal and storage in room temperature with time intervals 15 and 20 days.

Table - Drug-excipient ratio for compatibility study-

S.n.	Excipient	Ratio
1	Drug	1
2	Drug+Eudragit L-100	1:1
3	Drug+Ethylcellulose	1:1
4	Drug+PVA	1:1

PREPARATION OF BUDESONIDE LOADED MICROSPONGES-

Budesonide loded microsponges were prepared by quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method and using Eudragit L-100, ethyl cellulose, polyvinyl alcohol , ethanol and dichloromethane. Eudragit L-100 and ethyl cellulose was dissolved in ratio of ethanol and dichloromethane than added specific amount of budesonide. This mixture was added in aqueous solution of polyvinyl alcohol and continuous stirrer with magnetic stirrer for 8 hr at 500rpm.

Table - Formulation composition of Budesonide microsponges-

S.N.	BATCH CODE	AMOUNT OF DRUG (mg)	EUDRAGIT L-100 (mg)	ETHYL CELLULOSE (mg)	DCM:ETHANO L (10:10) (ml)	PVA(%)	WATER (ml)
1	F1	100	50	50	20	0.5	500
2	F2	100	100	100	20	0.5	500
3	F3	100	150	150	20	0.5	500
4	F4	100	200	200	20	0.5	500
5	F5	100	250	250	20	0.5	500
6	F6	100	300	300	20	0.5	500
7	F7	100	350	350	20	0.5	500
8	F8	100	400	400	20	0.5	500
9	F9	100	450	450	20	0.5	500
10	F10	100	500	500	20	0.5	500
11	F11	100	550	550	20	0.5	500
12	F12	100	600	600	20	0.5	500

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PREFORMULATION STUDIES-

Preparation of calibration curve of budesonide in methanol- The UV absorbance data was found to be 243.40 nm and concentration estimates of budesonide showed linearity (r^2 0.993). The concentration was taken from the range 5 to 250 µg/ml and it follows the Beer-lambert law. Calibration curve are obtained the slope value 0.036 and intercept value 0.027 respectively. The result are shown UV spectra in fig 3.3, standard absorbance table 3.4 and standard curve fig 3.5.

Fig3.1 -UV

spectrum of budesonide in methanol
Table 3.1- Data for calibration curve of budesonide in methanol-

S.n.	Conc.(µg/ml)	Absorbance ± S.D.
1	5	0.203±0.002
2	10	0.438±0.001
3	15	0.596±0.0015
4	20	0.753±0.001
5	25	0.923±0.004

Fig 3.2– Calibration curve of budesonide in methanol

3.1.2 Preparation calibration curve of budesonide in phosphate buffer pH 6.8- The UV absorbance was found to be 247.40 nm and concentration estimates of budesonide showed linearity (r^2 0.990). Calibration curve are obtained the slope value 0.006 and intercept value 0.050 respectively. The results are shown UV spectra in fig 3.6, standard absorbance table 3.7 and standard curve fig 3.8.

Fig3.3- UV spectrum of budesonide in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Table 3.2 - Data for calibration curve of budesonide in phosphate buffer pH 6.8-

S.n.	Conc.(µg/ml)	Absorbance ± S.D.
1	20	0.197±0.002
2	40	0.344±0.0015
3	60	0.403±0.002
4	80	0.569±0.002
5	100	0.677±0.0015
6	120	0.797±0.002
7	140	0.897±0.0005

Fig 3.4 - Calibration curve of budesonide in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

3.1.3 Preparation Calibration curve of budesonide in 0.1 N Hcl-

The UV absorbance data was found to be 247.40 nm and concentration estimates of budesonide showed linearity (r^2 0.996). Calibration curve are obtained the slope value 0.006 and intercept value 0.010 respectively. The results are shown UV spectra in fig 3.9, standard absorbance table 3.10 and standard curve fig 3.11.

Fig 3.5 - UV spectrum of budesonide in 0.1N Hcl

Table 3.3 - Data for calibration curve of budesonide in 0.1N Hcl-

S.n.	Conc(µg/ml)	Absorbance ±S.D.
1	20	0.146±0.002
2	40	0.224±0.0026
3	60	0.356±0.002
4	80	0.492±0.0025
5	100	0.621±0.003
6	120	0.781±0.0015
7	140	0.904±0.001

Fig 3.6- Calibration curve of budesonide in 0.1N HCl

Preparation calibration curve of budesonide in water- The UV absorbance data was found to be 246.80 nm and concentration estimates of budesonide showed linearity (r^2 0.994). The calibration curve are obtained slope value 0.008 and intercept value 0.029 respectively . The results are shown UV spectra in fig 3.12, table standard absorbance 3.13 and fig standard curve 3.14.

Fig 3.7- UV spectrum of budesonide in water

Table 3.4- Data for calibration curve of budesonide in water-

S.n.	Conc($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance \pm S.D.
1	20	0.208 \pm 0.002
2	40	0.421 \pm 0.002
3	60	0.556 \pm 0.002
4	80	0.721 \pm 0.001
5	100	0.887 \pm 0.002

Fig 3.8- Calibration curve of budesonide in water**Determination of partition coefficient-**

Partition coefficient was determined by the shake flask method in n-octanol and distilled water. Partition coefficient are used in determination of the lipophilicity of drug molecule. The log P is found to be 2.42 shows in table 4.5.

Table 3.5 - Partition coefficient value of budesonide-

Experimental value (log P)	Reference value (log P)
2.42	2.48

Solubility analysis-

Solubility of budesonide are determined in different solvent like methanol, 0.1 N HCl, water and phosphate-buffer pH 6.8 are found to be different concentration 19.666, 26, 2.5625 and 27.375 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The budesonide are highly soluble in methano and low soluble in water. The results are shown in table 4.6.

Table 3.6- Solubility analysis of budesonide-

Sn.	Solvent	λ_{max}	Absorbance	Conc.($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount
1	Methanol	243.60	0.735	19.66	19.666
2	0.1 N HCl	246	0.144	14.375	14.375
3	Water	246.40	0.234	25.625	2.5625
4	Phosphate buffer pH 6.8	246.20	0.125	12	12

Fig 3.9- Solubility analysis of Budesonide in different solvent**DRUG-EXCIPIENT INTERACTION STUDIES-****1. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy-**

FTIR spectra was obtained by the FTIR spectrophotometer. FTIR spectra of drug, physical mixture of drug and eudragit L-100 , drug and ethyl cellulose, drug and PVA were incorporated in potassium bromide discs. The peaks are shown in different fig 3.9,3.10, 3.11, 3.12.

Fig

3.11- FTIR spectrum of (Budesonide+Eudragit L-100)

Fig 3.12-

FTIR spectrum of (Budesonide+Ethylcellulose)

Fig 3.13- FTIR spectrum of (Budesonide + Polyvinyl alcohol)

2. Scanning Electron Microscopy-

The morphology and surface characteristics of the microsponges was studies using SEM. All sample was coated with gold palladium alloy under vacuum and SEM was carried out on formulation F5. The particle size range 100µm and result are shown in fig 3.13.

Fig 3.14- SEM analysis of Budesonide loded microsponges

Fig 3.15- SEM analysis of Budesonide microsponges

Fig 3.16- SEM analysis of Budesonide microsponges

3. Differential Scanning Calorimetry- DSC was carried out on formulation F3 and F5.

3.17- DSC spectra of formulation F3

fig

fig 3.17- DSC spectra of formulation F5

4. X-Ray Diffractometry Study- Crystalline nature of microsponges was studied using X-R.D and X-RD was carried out on formulation F3 and F5. The results are shown in fig 3.14 and 3.15.

Fig 3.18 - X-

RD spectrum of formulation (F3)

Table 3.7 - Peak list of X-RD report (F3)-

Pos. [°2Th.]	FWHM [°2Th.]	d-spacing [Å]	Rel. Int. [%]	Area [cts*°2Th.]
6.0880	0.3346	14.51787	57.89	67.14
12.0969	0.3346	7.31653	42.49	49.29
14.4145	0.4015	6.14493	48.64	67.71
15.4808	0.3346	5.72401	100.00	115.99
16.0151	0.3011	5.53422	86.02	89.80
16.8609	0.4015	5.25847	38.15	53.10
18.5027	0.4015	4.79540	37.82	52.65
21.2647	0.8029	4.17837	21.90	60.97
22.9429	0.5353	3.87641	32.78	60.84

Fig 3.19 - X-RD spectrum of (F5)
Table 3.8 - Peake list of X-RD report (F5)-

Pos. [°2Th.]	FWHM [°2Th.]	d-spacing [Å]	Rel. Int. [%]	Area [cts*°2Th.]
6.3559	0.3346	13.90646	38.82	61.61
12.4041	0.1004	7.13603	58.37	27.79
14.8186	0.4015	5.97828	57.30	109.12
15.4786	0.1506	5.72483	85.95	61.38
15.7973	0.2007	5.61002	100.00	95.22
18.6995	0.4015	4.74539	34.29	65.30
21.3858	0.8029	4.15499	21.47	81.77
23.1246	0.4015	3.84635	26.18	49.86

Production yield, entrapment efficiency and drug content- The percentage of production yield, entrapment efficiency and drug content are summarized in table 3.9.

Table 3.9- Percentage of production yield, entrapment efficiency and drug content

Formulation code	Drug:Polymer	Entrapment efficiency(%)	Production yield (%)	Drug content (%)
F1	1:1	35	50	69.325
F2	1:2	41	75	74.259
F3	1:3	33.333	89.333	72.345
F4	1:4	45	75	72.345
F5	1:5	55	92.2	82.592
F6	1:6	44	82.666	74.444
F7	1:7	52	83.428	69.135
F8	1:8	35	82.875	55
F9	1:9	41.333	85.333	59.197
F10	1:10	47	57	69.629
F11	1:11	32.612	72.727	64.382
F12	1:12	48.222	81.333	43.641

DRUG RELEASE PROFILE OF DIFFERENT FORMULATON-

Table 3.10 - Drug release profile of F1-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.031	0.25	0.0025	0.0125	2.25	2.25	2.25
1	0.035	0.75	0.0075	0.0375	6.75	6.7625	6.7625
2	0.041	1.5	0.015	0.075	13.5	13.5375	13.5375
3	0.102	2.8	0.028	0.14	25.2	25.275	25.275
4	0.132	3.657143	0.036571	0.182857	32.91429	33.05429	33.05429
5	0.163	4.542857	0.045429	0.227143	40.88571	41.06857	41.06857

6	0.194	5.428571	0.054286	0.271429	48.85714	49.08429	49.08429
7	0.226	6.342857	0.063429	0.317143	57.08571	57.35714	57.35714
8	0.25	7.028571	0.070286	0.351429	63.25714	63.57429	63.57429
9	0.268	7.542857	0.075429	0.377143	67.88571	68.23714	68.23714
10	0.307	8.657143	0.086571	0.432857	77.91429	78.29143	78.29143
11	0.312	8.8	0.088	0.44	79.2	79.63286	79.63286
12	0.321	9.057143	0.090571	0.452857	81.51429	81.95429	81.95429

Fig 3.20- Drug release profile of F1

Table 3.11 - Drug release profile of F2-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.025	0.6	0.006	0.03	5.4	5.4	5.4
1	0.035	0.885714	0.008857	0.044286	7.971429	8.001429	8.001429
2	0.091	2.485714	0.024857	0.124286	22.37143	22.41571	22.41571
3	0.109	3	0.03	0.15	27	27.12429	27.12429
4	0.131	3.628571	0.036286	0.181429	32.65714	32.80714	32.80714
5	0.169	4.714286	0.047143	0.235714	42.42857	42.61	42.61
6	0.196	5.485714	0.054857	0.274286	49.37143	49.60714	49.60714
7	0.221	6.2	0.062	0.31	55.8	56.07429	56.07429
8	0.245	6.885714	0.068857	0.344286	61.97143	62.28143	62.28143
9	0.262	7.371429	0.073714	0.368571	66.34286	66.68714	66.68714
10	0.301	8.485714	0.084857	0.424286	76.37143	76.74	76.74
11	0.321	9.057143	0.090571	0.452857	81.51429	81.93857	81.93857
12	0.329	9.285714	0.092857	0.464286	83.57143	84.02429	84.02429

Fig 3.21- Drug release profile of F2

Table 3.12 - Drug release profile of F3-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.035	0.75	0.0075	0.0375	6.75	6.75	1.35
1	0.052	2.875	0.02875	0.14375	25.875	25.9125	5.1825
2	0.089	7.5	0.075	0.375	67.5	67.64375	13.52875
3	0.115	10.75	0.1075	0.5375	96.75	97.125	19.425
4	0.149	15	0.15	0.75	135	135.5375	27.1075
5	0.167	17.25	0.1725	0.8625	155.25	156	31.2
6	0.195	20.75	0.2075	1.0375	186.75	187.6125	37.5225
7	0.221	24	0.24	1.2	216	217.0375	43.4075
8	0.254	28.125	0.28125	1.40625	253.125	254.325	50.865
9	0.276	30.875	0.30875	1.54375	277.875	279.2813	55.85625
10	0.309	35	0.35	1.75	315	316.5438	63.30875
11	0.342	39.125	0.39125	1.95625	352.125	353.875	70.775
12	0.351	40.25	0.4025	2.0125	362.25	364.2063	72.84125

Fig 3.22- Drug release profile of F3

Table 3.13 - Drug release profile of F4-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.037	1	0.01	0.05	9	9	1.8
1	0.088	7.375	0.07375	0.36875	66.375	66.425	13.285
2	0.133	13	0.13	0.65	117	117.3688	23.47375
3	0.143	14.25	0.1425	0.7125	128.25	128.9	25.78
4	0.169	17.5	0.175	0.875	157.5	158.2125	31.6425
5	0.201	21.5	0.215	1.075	193.5	194.375	38.875
6	0.24	26.375	0.26375	1.31875	237.375	238.45	47.69
7	0.252	27.875	0.27875	1.39375	250.875	252.1938	50.43875
8	0.281	31.5	0.315	1.575	283.5	284.8938	56.97875
9	0.306	34.625	0.34625	1.73125	311.625	313.2	62.64
10	0.33	37.625	0.37625	1.88125	338.625	340.3563	68.07125
11	0.351	40.25	0.4025	2.0125	362.25	364.1313	72.82625
12	0.361	41.5	0.415	2.075	373.5	375.5125	75.1025

fig 3.23- Drug release profile of F4

Table 3.14 - Drug release profile of F5-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cumulative drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.025	0.6	0.006	0.03	5.4	5.4	5.4
1	0.065	1.742857	0.017429	0.087143	15.68571	15.71571	15.71571
2	0.091	2.485714	0.024857	0.124286	22.37143	22.45857	22.45857
3	0.122	3.371429	0.033714	0.168571	30.34286	30.46714	30.46714
4	0.162	4.514286	0.045143	0.225714	40.62857	40.79714	40.79714
5	0.184	5.142857	0.051429	0.257143	46.28571	46.51143	46.51143
6	0.203	5.685714	0.056857	0.284286	51.17143	51.42857	51.42857
7	0.218	6.114286	0.061143	0.305714	55.02857	55.31286	55.31286
8	0.253	7.114286	0.071143	0.355714	64.02857	64.33429	64.33429
9	0.285	8.028571	0.080286	0.401429	72.25714	72.61286	72.61286
10	0.324	9.142857	0.091429	0.457143	82.28571	82.68714	82.68714
11	0.352	9.942857	0.099429	0.497143	89.48571	89.94286	89.94286
12	0.375	10.6	0.106	0.53	95.4	95.89714	95.89714

Fig 3.24- Drug release profile of F5**Table 3.15 - Drug release profile of F6-**

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.0295	0.0625	0.000625	0.003125	0.5625	0.5625	0.1125
1	0.055	3.25	0.0325	0.1625	29.25	29.25313	5.850625
2	0.087	7.25	0.0725	0.3625	65.25	65.4125	13.0825
3	0.113	10.5	0.105	0.525	94.5	94.8625	18.9725
4	0.152	15.375	0.15375	0.76875	138.375	138.9	27.78
5	0.169	17.5	0.175	0.875	157.5	158.2688	31.65375
6	0.215	23.25	0.2325	1.1625	209.25	210.125	42.025
7	0.241	26.5	0.265	1.325	238.5	239.6625	47.9325

8	0.27	30.125	0.30125	1.50625	271.125	272.45	54.49
9	0.298	33.625	0.33625	1.68125	302.625	304.1313	60.82625
10	0.307	34.75	0.3475	1.7375	312.75	314.4313	62.88625
11	0.331	37.75	0.3775	1.8875	339.75	341.4875	68.2975
12	0.341	39	0.39	1.95	351	352.8875	70.5775

Fig 3.25 - Drug release profile of F6

Table 3.16 - Drug release profile of F7-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cumulative drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.03	0.742857	0.007429	0.037143	6.685714	6.685714	6.685714
1	0.042	1.085714	0.010857	0.054286	9.771429	9.808571	9.808571
2	0.05	1.314286	0.013143	0.065714	11.82857	11.88286	11.88286
3	0.082	2.228571	0.022286	0.111429	20.05714	20.12286	20.12286
4	0.093	2.542857	0.025429	0.127143	22.88571	22.99714	22.99714
5	0.123	3.4	0.034	0.17	30.6	30.72714	30.72714
6	0.136	3.771429	0.037714	0.188571	33.94286	34.11286	34.11286
7	0.169	4.714286	0.047143	0.235714	42.42857	42.61714	42.61714
8	0.206	5.771429	0.057714	0.288571	51.94286	52.17857	52.17857
9	0.236	6.628571	0.066286	0.331429	59.65714	59.94571	59.94571
10	0.253	7.114286	0.071143	0.355714	64.02857	64.36	64.36
11	0.299	8.428571	0.084286	0.421429	75.85714	76.21286	76.21286
12	0.315	8.885714	0.088857	0.444286	79.97143	80.39286	80.39286

Fig 3.26 – Drug release profile of F7

Table 3.17 - Drug release profile of F8-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.034	0.625	0.00625	0.03125	5.625	5.625	1.125
1	0.066	4.625	0.04625	0.23125	41.625	41.65625	8.33125
2	0.085	7	0.07	0.35	63	63.23125	12.64625
3	0.102	9.125	0.09125	0.45625	82.125	82.475	16.495
4	0.117	11	0.11	0.55	99	99.45625	19.89125
5	0.139	13.75	0.1375	0.6875	123.75	124.3	24.86
6	0.148	14.875	0.14875	0.74375	133.875	134.5625	26.9125
7	0.174	18.125	0.18125	0.90625	163.125	163.8688	32.77375
8	0.195	20.75	0.2075	1.0375	186.75	187.6563	37.53125
9	0.211	22.75	0.2275	1.1375	204.75	205.7875	41.1575
10	0.241	26.5	0.265	1.325	238.5	239.6375	47.9275
11	0.251	27.75	0.2775	1.3875	249.75	251.075	50.215
12	0.279	31.25	0.3125	1.5625	281.25	282.6375	56.5275

Fig 3.27 - Drug release profile of F8

Table 3.18 - Drug release profile of F9-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.035	0.75	0.0075	0.0375	6.75	6.75	6.75
1	0.059	1.571429	0.015714	0.078571	14.14286	14.18036	14.18036
2	0.089	2.428571	0.024286	0.121429	21.85714	21.93571	21.93571
3	0.121	3.342857	0.033429	0.167143	30.08571	30.20714	30.20714
4	0.149	4.142857	0.041429	0.207143	37.28571	37.45286	37.45286
5	0.174	4.857143	0.048571	0.242857	43.71429	43.92143	43.92143
6	0.186	5.2	0.052	0.26	46.8	47.04286	47.04286
7	0.226	6.342857	0.063429	0.317143	57.08571	57.34571	57.34571
8	0.265	7.457143	0.074571	0.372857	67.11429	67.43143	67.43143
9	0.272	7.657143	0.076571	0.382857	68.91429	69.28714	69.28714
10	0.288	8.114286	0.081143	0.405714	73.02857	73.41143	73.41143
11	0.332	9.371429	0.093714	0.468571	84.34286	84.74857	84.74857
12	0.345	9.742857	0.097429	0.487143	87.68571	88.15429	88.15429

Fig 3.28- Drug release profile of F9**Table 3.19 - Drug release profile of F10-**

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.035	0.75	0.0075	0.0375	6.75	6.75	1.35
1	0.045	2	0.02	0.1	18	5.914286	1.182857
2	0.06	3.875	0.03875	0.19375	34.875	34.975	6.995
3	0.086	7.125	0.07125	0.35625	64.125	64.31875	12.86375
4	0.097	8.5	0.085	0.425	76.5	76.85625	15.37125
5	0.109	10	0.1	0.5	90	90.425	18.085
6	0.1232	11.775	0.11775	0.58875	105.975	106.475	21.295

7	0.149	15	0.15	0.75	135	135.5888	27.11775
8	0.169	17.5	0.175	0.875	157.5	158.25	31.65
9	0.203	21.75	0.2175	1.0875	195.75	196.625	39.325
10	0.216	23.375	0.23375	1.16875	210.375	211.4625	42.2925
11	0.236	25.875	0.25875	1.29375	232.875	234.0438	46.80875
12	0.256	28.375	0.28375	1.41875	255.375	256.6688	51.33375

Fig 3.29 - Drug release profile of F10

Table 3.20 - Drug release profile of F11-

Time (hrs.)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	% CDR
0.5	0.018	0.4	0.004	0.02	3.6	3.6	3.6
1	0.021	0.485714	0.004857	0.024286	4.371429	4.391429	4.391429
2	0.034	0.857143	0.008571	0.042857	7.714286	7.738571	7.738571
3	0.075	2.028571	0.020286	0.101429	18.25714	18.3	18.3
4	0.082	2.228571	0.022286	0.111429	20.05714	20.15857	20.15857
5	0.112	3.085714	0.030857	0.154286	27.77143	27.88286	27.88286
6	0.127	3.514286	0.035143	0.175714	31.62857	31.78286	31.78286
7	0.14	3.885714	0.038857	0.194286	34.97143	35.14714	35.14714
8	0.158	4.4	0.044	0.22	39.6	39.79429	39.79429
9	0.189	5.285714	0.052857	0.264286	47.57143	47.79143	47.79143
10	0.2	5.6	0.056	0.28	50.4	50.66429	50.66429
11	0.211	5.914286	0.059143	0.295714	53.22857	53.50857	53.50857
12	0.223	6.257143	0.062571	0.312857	56.31429	56.61	56.61

Fig 3.30- Drug release profile of F11

Table 3.21 - Drug release profile of F12-

Time (hr.)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Amount (1ml)	Amount (5ml)	Amount (900ml)	Cum. Drug release	%CDR
0.5	0.01	0.171429	0.001714	0.008571	1.542857	1.542857	1.542857
1	0.032	0.8	0.008	0.04	7.2	7.208571	7.208571
2	0.042	1.085714	0.010857	0.054286	9.771429	9.811429	9.811429
3	0.055	1.457143	0.014571	0.072857	13.11429	13.16857	13.16857
4	0.075	2.028571	0.020286	0.101429	18.25714	18.33	18.33
5	0.082	2.228571	0.022286	0.111429	20.05714	20.15857	20.15857
6	0.112	3.085714	0.030857	0.154286	27.77143	27.88286	27.88286
7	0.12	3.314286	0.033143	0.165714	29.82857	29.98286	29.98286
8	0.148	4.114286	0.041143	0.205714	37.02857	37.19429	37.19429
9	0.176	4.914286	0.049143	0.245714	44.22857	44.43429	44.43429
10	0.177	4.942857	0.049429	0.247143	44.48571	44.73143	44.73143
11	0.182	5.085714	0.050857	0.254286	45.77143	46.01857	46.01857
12	0.195	5.457143	0.054571	0.272857	49.11429	49.36857	49.36857

Fig 3.31 - Drug release profile F12

Cumulative amount of drug release-
Table3.22 - Percent cumulative release of budesonide loaded microsponges-

TIME (hrs.)	% CUMULATIVE DRUG RELEASE											
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
0.5	2.25	5.4	1.35	1.8	5.4	0.1125	6.685714	1.125	6.75	1.35	3.6	1.542857
1	6.7625	8.001429	5.1825	13.285	15.71571	5.850625	9.808571	8.33125	14.18036	11.82857	4.391429	7.208571
2	13.5375	22.41571	13.52875	23.47375	22.45857	13.0825	11.88286	12.64625	21.93571	6.995	7.738571	9.811429
3	25.275	27.12429	19.425	25.78	30.46714	18.9725	20.12286	16.495	30.20714	12.86375	18.3	13.16857
4	33.05429	32.80714	27.1075	31.6425	40.79714	27.78	22.99714	19.89125	37.45286	15.37125	20.15857	18.33
5	41.06857	42.61	31.2	38.875	46.51143	31.65375	30.72714	24.86	43.92143	18.085	27.88286	20.15857
6	49.08429	49.60714	37.5225	47.69	51.42857	42.025	34.11286	26.9125	47.04286	21.295	31.78286	27.88286
7	57.35714	56.07429	43.4075	50.43875	55.31286	47.9325	42.61714	32.77375	57.34571	27.11775	35.14714	29.98286
8	63.57429	62.28143	50.865	56.97875	64.33429	54.49	52.17857	37.53125	67.43143	31.65	39.79429	37.19429
9	68.23714	66.68714	55.85625	62.64	72.61286	60.82625	59.94571	41.1575	69.28714	39.325	47.79143	44.43429
10	78.29143	76.74	63.30875	68.07125	82.68714	62.88625	64.36	47.9275	73.41143	42.2925	50.66429	44.73143
11	79.63286	81.93857	70.775	72.82625	89.94286	68.2975	76.21286	50.215	84.74857	46.80875	53.50857	46.01857
12	81.95429	84.02429	72.84125	75.1025	95.89714	70.5775	80.39286	56.5275	88.15429	51.33375	56.61	49.36857

Fig 3.32 - Percentage cumulative drug release of different formulation

Drug release kinetics of optimized formulation F5

Table 3.23 - Drug release kinetic of batch F5-

Time (hrs.)	Log time	Square root of time	% Cumulative drug release	Log % Cumulative drug release	% Cumulative drug remaining	Log % Cumulative drug remaining
0.5	-0.30103	0.707107	5.4	0.732394	100	2
1	0	1	15.71571	1.196334	84.28429	1.925747
2	0.30103	1.414214	22.45857	1.351382	77.54143	1.889534
3	0.477121	1.732051	30.46714	1.483839	69.53286	1.84219
4	0.60206	2	40.79714	1.61063	59.20286	1.772343
5	0.69897	2.236068	46.51143	1.66756	53.48857	1.728261
6	0.778151	2.44949	51.42857	1.711204	48.57143	1.686381
7	0.845098	2.645751	55.31286	1.742826	44.68714	1.650183
8	0.90309	2.828427	64.33429	1.808443	35.66571	1.552251
9	0.954243	3	72.61286	1.861014	27.38714	1.437547
10	1	3.162278	82.68714	1.917438	17.31286	1.238369
11	1.041393	3.316625	89.94286	1.953967	10.05714	1.002474
12	1.079181	3.464102	95.89714	1.981806	4.10286	0.613087

Fig.3.33 - Zero order release kinetic of F5

3.34- First order kinetic of F5

Fig 3.35– Higuchi model release kinetics of F5

Fig 3.36- Korsmeyer-peppas model release kinetics of F5

Table 3.24 - Release pattern of Budesonide microsponges-

Zero order kinetic	First order kinetic	Higuchi model	Korsmeyer-Peppas model	
r ²	r ²	r ²	r ²	N
0.992	0.851	0.972	0.982	0.543

DISCUSSION:

The aim of this work to utilize the colon specific drug delivery for treatment of several colonic diseases like chron’s disease, ulcerative disease and colon cancer. Budesonide are low water solubility and poor bioavailability of budesonide is the challenging problem facing by the formulation scientist. Budesonide loaded microsponges are designed to deliver a pharmaceutically active ingredient efficiently at minimum dose and also to enhance stability, reduce side effect, modify drug release profile and used pH sensitive polymer like Eudragit L-100 which can be bypasses the upper GIT. Budesonide loaded microsponges are overcome the above problem by increasing the solubility to increase the bioavailability.

CONCLUSION

Budesonide loaded microsponges are prepared by quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method. FTIR studies are confirm the compatibility of budesonide with the various excipient used in study and DSC, SEM, X-RD study are used in evaluation of microsponges.

Preparation of budesonide loaded microsponges using the quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method and used the different polymer like eudragit L-100 and ethyl cellulose, PVA and DCM as a stabilizer is found to feasible, economical and more productive. Budesonide loaded microspoonge (batch 5) has found to be optimum formulation with reference to various physicochemical characterization such as drug content, entrapment efficiency and dissolution profile.

Dissolution profile and solubility are improved for the budesonide loaded microsponges compared to other formulation. These study are mainly used in targeting drug delivery system.

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BIOLOGICAL NOMENCLATURE

Name:-Budesonide

Categories:-Corticosteroid

IUPAC Name:-16,17-(Butylenebis(oxy))-11,21-dihydroxypregna-1,4-diene-3,20dione

Solubility:-It is soluble in alcohol

Melting point:-226°C

Dose:-9 mg/day

Discription:-It is white powders

Excretion:-Renal(60%)

Protein binging:-85-90%

Elimination t_{1/2}:- 2-4hr

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